

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Polymorphism in *Oryza malampuzhaensis*

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Studies on *O. malampuzhaensis* Krishn. et Chandn., a tetraploid wild rice from South India, are scanty because it is poorly represented in germplasm and herbarium collections. We compared recent collections of this taxon: Ac 42 from the National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources Regional Station, Trichur, India, and four accessions collected from natural habitats along the western Ghat, South India (Ac 51 from Parambikulam, Ac 55 from Nilambur, Ac 56 from Vellani, and Ac 57 from Peechi).

Tillers at the 3-leaf stage were separated from the perennial parent plant and grown in pots, with four replications. A minimum 5 tillers/plant were observed at appropriate stages of development (see table).

Accessions varied in all characters evaluated except chromosome number. Meiotic studies showed regular forma-

Variation in quantitative and qualitative characters of 5 accessions of tetraploid wild rice from South India.

Character	Mean					LSD (p=0.05)
	Ac 42	Ac 51	Ac 55	Ac 56	Ac 57	
Boot leaf length (cm)	27.5	25.3	20.1	23.3	21.0	2.28
Boot leaf width (cm)	2.0	1.5	1.6	1.5	1.5	0.09
Peduncle length (cm)	60.1	64.7	47.2	50.9	57.9	6.59
1st internode length (cm)	28.2	25.0	20.0	20.5	23.2	2.73
Culm length (cm)	127.7	115.0	73.1	80.9	88.5	10.21
Panicle length (cm)	21.8	19.7	17.8	21.4	18.7	1.93
Av length of primary branch (cm)	12.3	13.5	9.1	10.7	9.9	1.96
No. of primary branches/panicle	9.7	6.6	6.7	6.1	6.2	0.74
No. of spikelets/panicle	166.6	118.3	81.0	88.2	82.9	16.02
Ligule length (mm)	3.1	2.9	1.8	2.7	2.7	0.17
Spikelet length (mm)	6.1	5.6	4.9	5.8	5.4	0.16
Spikelet width (mm)	2.3	2.5	2.2	2.3	2.4	0.12
Spikelet length/width ratio	2.6	2.3	2.2	2.5	2.2	0.15
Spikelet thickness (mm)	1.5	1.5	1.3	1.4	1.4	0.05
Sterile glume length (mm)	1.2	1.5	1.0	1.5	1.3	0.12
Awn length (cm)	0.4	1.4	0.7	0.7	0.9	0.18
Chromosome number (n)	24	24	24	24	24	
Pollen sterility (%)	8.9	5.4	10.9	26.4	65.7	
Ligule fringing	Long, very dense	Short, sparse	Short, dense	Short, very sparse	Very long, moderately dense	
Stigma color	Very dark purple	Dark purple	White	Purple	Dark purple	
Blooming time	0730-1030 h	0800-1200 h	0800-1200 h	0800-1400 h	0730-1500 h	

tion of 24 bivalents at diakinesis. It is evident this taxon is polymorphic, with much wider distribution than was

hitherto known. Further studies are needed to elucidate its taxonomic status and evolutionary position. ■

Breeding methods

Identifying maintainers and restorers of CMS lines for hybrid rice breeding

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We crossed 40 rice cultivars as pollen parents with cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines V20 A, V97 A, Pankhari 203 A, IR46826 A, IR54752 A, and IR54753 A, to identify maintainers and restorers for varying agroclimate and

Table 1. Maintainers and restorers in the CMS lines of rice.

Cultivar	Classification ^a					
	V20 A	V97 A	Pankhari 203 A	IR46826 A	IR54752 A	IR54753 A
Bala	PR	M	PR	PR	R	R
Kiran	PR	PR	PR	PR	R	PR
Kanchan	PR	R	PM	PR	PM	PM
Browngora	PM	R	PR	PR	PR	PR
Birsa Dhan 101	PM	PR	PM	PR	PR	PR
Birsa Dhan 202	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM
Basmati 370	R	PR	PM	PM		PM
Rajendra Dhan 202	R	PR	PM	R	R	PR
Sita	PR	PR	PM	PM	PR	PM
BR8	PM	PM	PR	R	M	PR
BR9	PM	M	PR	PR	PR	PM
RAU4045-10	M	M			PM	PR
Akashi	M	PR		R		PR
Rasi	PR	PR	PR	PR	PR	M
Ratna	PR	R	PM	R	R	PR
Mahsuri	PM	R	PM	PR	PR	PR

continued next page.

Table 1 continued

Cultivar	Classification ^a					
	V20 A	V97 A	Pankhari 203 A	IR46826 A	IR54752 A	IR54753 A
Kalinga 3	PM	PR	PM	PR	PR	R
Dular	PR	PM	PM	PR	PM	R
Jaya	PM	PM	-	PM	PM	-
BG380-2	PR	PR	-	PR	PR	PR
BAU4045-2BI	PR	PR	PM	PR	PR	PM
BAU151-52	M	PM	PM	PR	PR	PM
NDR85	R	PM	PR	PM	R	PR
BAU148-28	R	PR	PR	PM	PR	PR
BAU148-30	PM	M	PM	PR	R	PM
ZHU XI-26	PR	PR	PM	PR	PR	M
IET7564	M	PM	PR	R	PM	R
Saket	PR	PM	-	R	PM	R
IET9789	R	PR	PR	PR	PR	-
IET9810	R	PR	PR	R	R	R
IET9815	R	R	PR	PR	PR	PR
VLK39	PR	PR	-	R	PR	PR
Sattari	PR	PR	-	PR	-	PR
Kalkari	PM	PR	-	-	M	PM
Neela	M	PR	PM	-	PR	PR
Sujata	PR	PR	PR	PR	-	PR
Archana	PR	PR	PR	PR	-	PR
RR51-1	PR	PR	-	R	PR	-
OR164-5	PR	PM	-	PM	PR	-
HPU734	PR	PM	PR	M	PR	-
IR50	R	R	-	-	-	-
IR88-30-3- 1-4-2	PR	PR	-	-	-	-
IR24594-204- 1-3-2-6-2	PM	PR	-	-	-	-
IR64	PR	PM	-	-	-	-
BG367-7	PR	R	-	-	-	-
Kalimeksi 77-5	PR	PR	-	-	-	-
IR62	PR	PR	-	-	-	-
SR4095-19-2-3-5-4	R	R	-	-	-	-
K438	R	PR	-	-	-	-
IR27078-3-6	PR	PM	-	-	-	-
IR19746-28-2-2-3	PM	PM	-	-	-	-
IR32093-B-1-B-23	PM	M	-	-	-	-
TKM6	PR	PM	-	-	-	-
IR912Y-KI	PR	PR	-	-	-	-
Tres Meses	PR	PM	-	-	-	-
IR29423-B-3-B-2-5-1	M	PM	-	-	-	-
S290	PR	PM	-	-	-	-
AC19-1-1	PM	PR	-	-	-	-
IR13155-60-3-1-3-1-1-3	M	PM	-	-	-	-
IR20897-B-6	PR	PM	-	-	-	-
IR29416-B-3-B-6-5-12	PR	PM	-	-	-	-
IR7790-18-1-2	PM	PR	-	-	-	-
IR28224-3-2-3-2	R	R	-	-	-	-

^aR = effective restorer, PR = partial restorer, PM = partial maintainer, M = effective maintainer.

Table 2. Isolation of maintainers and restorers of IR46828 A and IR54752 A.

Designation	Cross	Classification
TN8891	IR46828 A/IR36 P ₁	PR
TN8893	IR46828 A/IR36 P ₂	R
TN8895	IR46828 A/IR36 P ₃	PR
TN8897	IR46828 A/IR36 P ₄	R
TN8971	IR54752 A/IR35454-18-1-2-2-2 P ₁	R
TN8973	IR54752 A/IR35454-18-1-2-2-2 P ₂	PR
TN8983	IR54752 A/IR35293-178-2-3-1 P ₁	PR
TN8985	IR54752 A/IR35293-178-2-3-1 P ₂	R
TN9003	IR54752 A/IR28224-3-2-3-2 P ₁	R
TN9005	IR54752 A/IR28224-3-2-3-2 P ₂	PR
TN9015	IR54752 A/IR2307-247-2-2-3 P ₁	PR
TN9017	IR54152 A/IR2307-247-2-2-3 P ₂	R

biotic stresses. In addition, 23 more cultivars were crossed with V20 A and V97 A.

Pollen of each CMS line (tested by 1% iodine solution before crossing) was found to be highly sterile. The pollen parents and the F₁s were transplanted together to determine maintainers and restorers. Panicles were bagged before emergence.

On the basis of spikelet fertility, the cultivars were classified as effective restorer (>80% spikelet fertility), weak or partial restorer (40-79%), weak or partial maintainer (1-39%), and effective maintainer (<1%).

Effective restorers and maintainers for the CMS lines are in Table 1.

IR46826 A, IR54752 A, and IR54753 A were found suitable for rainfed low-lands in the plateau region of Bihar.

Spikelet fertility was observed at IRR1 on F₁ progenies (10 plants each) of IR46828 A and IR54752 A and single plant selections of elite cultivars. Single plant selections of cultivars showed R to PR reaction (Table 2), indicating different restoring ability. It is necessary to purify cultivars for fertility restoration ability before using them in developing F₁ rice hybrids. ■

Yield potential

Seed dormancy of rice varieties released by Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University (APAU)

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Seed dormancy is needed in rice varieties grown during wet season (kharif) in AP coastal districts, which are prone to suffer cyclones and heavy rains at harvest.

We evaluated seed dormancy of all rice varieties released by APAU. Seed samples were collected 30 d after flowering and moisture content brought to 13-14% by sun drying. Dormancy duration (period required